

Can soil organic carbon be sustainably increased?

An analysis based on general literature and EJP SOIL results performed for the European Soil Partnership General Assembly.

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1. Introduction – key messages

- The first priority is to preserve existing soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks before attempting to increase them. This is particularly true for peatlands, and other organic soils, which contain large carbon stocks accumulated over centuries or millennia. Their drainage, cultivation or degradation can release carbon much faster than it can be sequestered in mineral soils. Protecting existing SOC stocks often provides greater and more immediate climate benefits rather than rebuilding depleted stocks.
- SOC accumulation and soil carbon sequestration should be clearly distinguished (Don et al. 2023). SOC accumulation refers to an increase in measured SOC stocks over time. Soil carbon sequestration implies a net transfer of atmospheric CO₂ into soil carbon stocks relative to a defined baseline. Consequently, an increase in SOC stocks does not necessarily correspond to additional atmospheric CO₂ removal.

Figure 1 Carbon sequestration is the removal of C from the atmosphere and the storage, for example, in soil. In soils that lose SOC, the implementation of C-storing management practices may only lead to a reduction in C losses (C loss mitigation) rather than to real C sequestration. Source : Don et al. 2023

- Soil organic carbon is only one component of soil organic matter (SOM). Soil functions such as nutrient cycling, water retention, aggregate stability, biodiversity support and crop productivity depend on the quantity and quality of SOM as a whole, not only carbon. Therefore, increasing SOC should not be considered an objective in itself, but rather as a means to support soil functions and ecosystem services.
- The question “where should SOC be increased in the soil profile?” depends on the objective pursued. For erosion control, increasing SOC near the soil surface may be sufficient. For crop productivity and drought resilience, carbon enrichment should target the rooting zone. From a

climate mitigation perspective, the whole soil profile should be considered, as subsoil accounts for a large portion of SOC stocks, and generally exhibits longer residence times and less vulnerability to disturbance (Emde et al., 2025, Skadell et al., 2023).

- SOC can be increased through improved land management, but not everywhere, not indefinitely and not always sustainably. Soil carbon stocks tend towards a dynamic equilibrium determined by climate, soil properties, land use and management. Consequently, storage rates generally decline over time as soils approach a new equilibrium, while the stored carbon may be lost again if management changes or disturbances occur (Chenu et al. 2019).
- Finally, SOC storage should be considered within a broader sustainability framework. Management practices that increase SOC must also maintain or enhance other soil functions and avoid adverse environmental trade-offs, such as increased greenhouse gas emissions, nutrient losses, biodiversity impacts or excessive water use.

2. Increasing SOC: mechanisms, drivers and management options in agricultural soils

Soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks increase when carbon inputs to the soil exceed carbon losses. This can be achieved either by increasing carbon inputs through plant production and organic amendments, or by reducing carbon losses through mineralisation and erosion.

Increasing carbon inputs is generally considered the most robust pathway for enhancing SOC stocks. Additional carbon can be supplied through greater plant productivity, increased returns of crop residues, larger root inputs, or the application of exogenous organic matter. SOC stocks can also be preserved or increased by reducing carbon losses. This may result from lower soil erosion rates or from slower decomposition of soil organic matter. Stabilisation mechanisms, including organo-mineral interactions and physical protection within the soil matrix, slow mineralisation and enhance the persistence of newly added organic inputs.

A wide range of management options can therefore contribute to SOC sequestration by acting on one or several of these processes simultaneously (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Levers allowing to preserve or enhance SOC stocks in agricultural soils. Increasing inputs 1- increasing photosynthesis (cover crops, living mulches, intercrops, grassing inter-rows in vineyards and orchards, temporary leys, agroforestry, hedges) 2- banning residue management by fires, 3- returning crop residues to soil, 4- importing exogenous organic matter (manures, sewage sludge, composts, digestates, biochar, 5- grassland practices (grassing rather than mowing, moderate intensification of grasslands). Decreasing outputs: 6- mitigating erosion (no tillage, increasing soil cover with living or dead mulches, anti-erosive features, agroforestry), 7- reducing SOM mineralisation rates (no tillage). Adapted from Chenu et al. 2019

The quantification of soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration potential is essential for designing effective climate policies and certification frameworks. Current approaches range from Tier 2 methods based on empirical response factors, to Tier 3 process-based models simulating carbon dynamics, and more recently to data-driven approaches relying on large soil inventories and machine learning (Pacini et al., 2023; Schneider et al., 2021). These complementary approaches differ in data requirements, assumptions and intended applications, but all aim to estimate the additional SOC storage that can realistically be achieved under improved management (Chenu et al., 2026).

At the European scale, the EJP SOIL programme conducted a harmonised Tier 2 assessment across 23 European countries, evaluating ten management options for agricultural mineral soils (Seidel et al., 2026). The study estimated that their combined implementation could mitigate approximately 20–31% of current agricultural greenhouse gas emissions in the EU, although achievable potentials strongly depend on local conditions and implementation rates. National assessments conducted in several European countries, including France, Germany, Norway and Finland, similarly highlight substantial, but highly variable sequestration potentials depending on pedoclimatic conditions, management systems, adoption rates and economic constraints (Emde et al., 2025; Budai et al., 2024; Launay et al., 2021, Bamière et al. 2023). These diverse assessments demonstrate that moving from theoretical to "achievable" potential requires integrating biophysical, technical, and socio-economic constraints (Chenu et al., 2026; Seidel et al., 2026).

Figure 3. A tier 2 estimate of feasible carbon sequestration potential in European agricultural mineral soils through improved management. Left: Surface area on which the considered C-storing management options could be additionally implemented; right: Number of management options that could be additionally implemented together in Europe. Source: Seidel et al. 2026.

Recent meta-analyses and large-scale assessments consistently show that the effectiveness of management practices differs considerably. Agroforestry, diversified grasslands, cover crops and biochar generally show the largest SOC gains, whereas reduced tillage often produces marginal increases and organic agriculture effects are hampered by yield reduction (Fohrafellner et al. 2024; Seidel et al., 2026; Yin et al., 2025; Don et al. 2025). The effectiveness of SOC storing practices is strongly controlled by pedoclimatic constraints. Soil texture, climate and water availability, act as primary filters for the feasibility and success of management practices (Heller et al., 2024; Seidel et al., 2026; Vanwindekens et al., 2022; Ceriani et al., 2026).

Emerging strategies increasingly focus on crop roots as a major source of soil carbon inputs (Rasse et al., 2005). Optimized genotype selection can increase root-derived C inputs by 7–26% without compromising yields (Heinemann et al., 2023). Similarly, diversified species mixtures in temporary grasslands or agroforestry enhance root biomass, particularly in subsoils (Mortensen et al., 2025).

Evidence suggests that targeted mixtures combining complementary root traits may be more effective for SOC storage than increasing species richness alone (Mortensen et al., 2025).

Although quantitative estimates vary substantially depending on assumptions, time horizons, baselines and adoption rates, all assessments converge on two important conclusions. First, sequestration potentials are finite and decline over time as soils approach a new equilibrium. Second, the achievable potential strongly depends on local soil, climate and farming conditions, highlighting the need for context-specific assessments rather than universal sequestration targets.

3. Conditions for sustainable C sequestration in soil

Sustainable soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration must be evaluated through three main lenses: permanence, trade-offs with other environmental and societal goals and additionality (Maenhout et al., 2024; Don et al., 2024).

The challenge of permanence and vulnerability

Carbon sequestration in soils is inherently limited in time because soils progressively approach a new equilibrium, often within a few decades after management changes. As a result, sequestration rates decline over time and may become negligible after a few decades (Chenu et al. 2019). Moreover, stored carbon remains vulnerable to management reversal and climate disturbances (Apostolakis et al., 2026). Rising temperatures, altered moisture regimes and extreme climatic events may accelerate SOC losses and reduce the long-term effectiveness of sequestration efforts (Heinz et al., 2025; Calone et al., 2026; Tao et al., 2023).

Navigating multifunctional trade-offs and co-benefits

A sustainable increase in SOC must not degrade other soil functions. Synergies are often observed with biodiversity; for example, the application of external organic matter (EOM) generally enhances microbial biomass and activity (Latini et al., 2026). However, trade-offs with crop yields can be significant: a European meta-analysis reveals that conservation agriculture practices lead to an average cereal yield reduction of 3% and a 9% decrease in yield stability, particularly in clay-rich soils (Ceriani et al., 2026).

From an environmental perspective, the "non- offset" is a major concern. Increased emissions can reduce the climate benefits of C sequestration (Valkama et al., 2024). While biochar can reduce N₂O emissions by an average of 35% (Valkama et al., 2024), practices like leguminous cover crops or manure application can stimulate GHG fluxes, depending on the ratio and soil aeration (Valkama et al., 2024; Meng et al., 2024, Belleville et al., 2026). Furthermore, soil compaction from traffic can exacerbate emissions creating anaerobic microsites (Pulido-Moncada et al., 2022; Ten Damme et al. 2025). Regarding water, while SOC increases available water capacity, the use of cover crops may reduce groundwater recharge in dry regions, creating a trade-off between green and blue water resources (Blanchy et al., 2023). The development of multi-criteria tools like the SOMMIT Index (Calone et al., 2024) is essential to aggregate these complex factors and guide balanced policy decisions.

Ensuring additionality

Carbon sequestration claims should also satisfy the principle of additionality. In particular, the application of exogenous organic matter should correspond to a net transfer of carbon from previously unused or underutilised biomass resources, rather than to a simple redistribution of organic matter within agricultural systems (Don et al., 2024). Sustainable SOC strategies should therefore favour the mobilisation of additional carbon resources, such as urban biowaste or other currently underutilised biomass streams (Budai et al., 2024; Keel et al., 2025).

Sustainable SOC sequestration requires more than measurable increases in carbon stocks. Carbon gains must be additional, sufficiently durable and achieved without unacceptable environmental trade-offs. Furthermore, future SOC strategies should move beyond the evaluation of individual practices towards a whole-system perspective. At farm scale, practices are rarely implemented in isolation and their effects often interact. Ultimately, the objective should be to enhance soil functions and ecosystem services through management systems that contribute simultaneously to climate mitigation, climate adaptation, biodiversity conservation and sustainable agricultural production.

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